

FIBER OPTIC CABLE ASSEMBLY SPECIFICATION CHECKLIST FOR AVIONICS APPLICATIONS

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Introduction

In this paper the reader is provided a comprehensive fiber optic cable assembly specification checklist to consider for avionics applications. Its purpose is to facilitate supply chain utilization of unambiguous specifications, qualifications, and quality assurance standardization of avionics fiber optic cable assemblies. Fiber optic cable assemblies used for avionics application should be considered on a case-by-case basis as the performance, service life, reliability, supportability, and maintainability requirements of avionics systems vary between aircraft type (i.e., fixed wing or rotary), model, series, mission, etc.

At a minimum, the fiber optic cable assembly should have well-defined terminus endface geometry and manufacturing quality assurance test criteria. Material selection and termination process characteristics should provide consistent and repeatable adhesive bonding between the fiber and terminus. Special attention should be given to fabrication processes such as terminus cleanliness, epoxy injection technique and epoxy cure schedule. Quality assurance inspections performed after cable assembly fabrication include 100% visual (or machine vision) inspection and optical performance testing, and random sampling for temperature cycle, pull test, and endface geometry. Vigilant attention during fabrication and post fabrication inspections is advocated to screen out defective fiber optic cable assemblies prior to aircraft cable harness integration or weapons replaceable assembly or line replaceable module integration.

Avionics Fiber Optic Cable Assembly Checklists

Table 1 contains the proposed avionics optical fiber characteristics checklist parameters. Table 2 contains the proposed fiber optic cable checklist. Table 3 contains the proposed fiber optic cable assembly checklist, which includes connectors, termini, and terminated cable.

Table 1: Optical Fiber Characteristics Checklist

Environmental Tests	Optical Parameters	Optical Parameters (continued)	Mechanical Tests	Geometrical/Dimensional
Post life aging	Attenuation rate	Numerical aperture	Dynamic tensile strength	Core diameter
mechanical strippability	Attenuation uniformity	Polarization mode dispersion (lumped)	Mechanical strippability	Core ovality
Storage temperature	Bandwidth	Transient attenuation	Fiber curl	Cladding diameter
Temperature cycling	Chromatic dispersion		Tensile proof	Cladding ovality
Temperature life	Cut-off wavelength	<u>Material Tests</u>	Macrobending loss	Core-to-cladding eccentricity
Temperature/Humidity cycling	Macrobend attenuation	Fluid immersion aging	Microbending loss	Coating diameter
Thermal shock	Mode field diameter	Fungus resistance	Fatigue	Coating-to-cladding eccentricity
	Modal dispersion	Radiation resistance	<u>Visual Inspection</u>	Coating concentricity
		Salt spray	Fiber length	Coating uniformity
		Stress cracking factor	Fiber mass/unit length	

Table 2: Fiber Optic Cable Characteristics Checklist

Abrasion/scraping resistance	Corner bend	Flammability	Pressure withstand
Acid gas generation	Crosslink verification	Fluid immersion	Radial compression
Altitude cycling	Crosstalk	Freezing water immersion	Ribbon delamination
Attenuation rate	Crush	Fungus resistance	Shock
Bandwidth	Cyclic flexing	Halogen/toxicity content	Storage temperature
Cable-to-cable abrasion	Change in optical transmittance	Hosing	Temperature cycling
Cable jacket tear strength	Cold bend	Impact	Tensile loading and elongation
Cable element removability	Dripping	Jacket self adhesion/blocking	Thermal shock
Cable jacket material tensile strength & elongation	Dynamic bend	Knot	Toxicity index
Cable kinking	Electromagnetic effects	Life aging	Water absorption & Humidity
Cable shrinkage	Flame extinguishing	Marking Permanency	Weathering
Cable twist bending	Flame propagation	Operating tensile load	Weight
Color	Flaming smoke generation	Pressure (barometric)	Wicking

Table 3: Fiber Optic Cable Assembly, Connector, and Terminus Characteristics Checklist

Acidic atmosphere resistance	Cable pull out force	Connector terminus removal force	Ozone exposure
Bend sensitivity/loss	Cable seal flexing	Connector terminus retention force	Rain
Cable assembly altitude immersion cycling	Clamp/Tie loss	Connector vibration	Return loss
Cable assembly crush	Connector acoustic shock	Connector workmanship	Salt spray
Cable assembly endface geometry	Connector backshell attachment	Connector weight	Sand and dust
Cable assembly endface scratches, pits, etc.	Connector cleanability	Dormant life	Storage life
Cable assembly external bending moment	Connector coupling engagement torque	Flammability	Temperature life
Cable assembly fiber pistoning	Connector dustcover attachment	Flexural endurance	Terminus alignment sleeve dimensions
Cable assembly identification	Connector identification/markings	Fluid immersion	Terminus cable pull out force
Cable assembly impact	Connector insert retention axial strength	Fluid resistance	Terminus cleanliness
Cable assembly marking	Connector insert retention radial strength	Freezing rain/Icing	Terminus circular runout
Cable assembly mating durability	Connector interoperability	Fungus resistance	Terminus dimensions
Cable assembly mechanical shock	Connector maintenance aging	Humidity life	Terminus fiber pull out force
Cable assembly minimum cable bend radius	Connector mechanical shock	Insertion loss	Terminus identification
Cable assembly temp cycling	Connector screw thread	Life aging	Terminus inspection
Cable assembly temp-humidity cycling	Connector seal	Maintenance aging	Terminus tip geometry
Cable assembly thermal shock	Connector size	Nuclear radiation	Terminus weight
Cable assembly twist	Connector terminus insert force	Operational life	Terminus workmanship

Avionics Fiber Optic Cable Assembly Reliability

Although the subject of avionics fiber optic cable assembly *reliability* is not within the scope of this paper, a few words of caution are needed to avert any false takeaways from this assessment. Tables 1, 2 and 3 contain proposed avionics fiber optic cable assembly checklist parameters for beginning of life verification only. Parameters described in Tables 1 and 2 for optical fiber and optical fiber cable, respectively, are embedded in the fiber optic cable assembly checklist described in Table 3. The “reliability” of fiber optic cable assemblies however, is not implicitly contained within Tables 1, 2 and 3. Rather, a separate fiber optic cable assembly reliability test plan based on reliability engineering principles must be implemented.

The reliability test plan goal should be to demonstrate fiber optic cable assembly reliability with statistical confidence against a predetermined reliability goal. The first step in this process is to define all system stress contributors acting on the fiber optic cable assembly over its lifetime (including shipping, manufacturing, installation, and operational/deployment) [1]. From there, application of highly accelerated life testing can be applied to identify fiber optic cable assembly design flaws [2]. Reliability growth can be attained by the application of a structured process consisting of testing, data analysis (simulations and calculations), and corrective action to reduce or eliminate design, manufacturing, shipping/packaging and installation flaws. Quantitative metrics are necessary to measure fiber optic cable assembly reliability growth against a given reliability goal. In the future, checklists will be created to address fiber optic cable assembly reliability, end-to-end link reliability, and system reliability.

Conclusion

Avionics fiber optic cable assembly specification requires a multi-disciplinary approach that includes avionics, fiber optics, aircraft wiring, reliability, maintainability, logistics, quality assurance and manufacturing engineering inputs. It is our hope that the aerospace industry will evaluate this paper and formalize the specification of avionics fiber optic cable assemblies in the form of a new Society of Automotive Engineers aerospace standard or aerospace recommended practice document.

References

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